

Mechanistic aspects of the ligand substitution reaction of diaquaethylenediamine-platinum(II) ion with 2-thiouracil in aqueous medium

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Abstract : The interaction of the title complex with 2-thiouracil has been studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous medium as a function of [substrate complex], [ligand] and temperature at a particular pH 4.0. The reaction has been monitored at 322 nm where the spectral difference between the reactant and the product is maximum. The reactions have been studied under pseudo-first order conditions. The reaction proceeds in a two-step-consecutive manner (A → B → C); where the first step is the ligand dependent and the second step is ligand independent and is assigned to formation of chelate ring. The reaction rate increases with increase in [ligand] before reaching a limiting value which is probably due to the completion of the outer-sphere association complex formation. At this stage the interchange of the ligands from the outer-sphere to the inner-sphere occurs. The activation parameters calculated from Eyring plots are : $\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 18.3 \pm 1.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -225 \pm 6 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 25.9 \pm 1.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -148 \pm 4.5 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Based on the kinetic and activation parameters an associative interchange mechanism is proposed for the interaction processes. The product of the reaction has been characterized with the help of IR and ESI-MS spectroscopic analysis.

Keywords : Kinetics, platinum(II), 2-thiouracil, mechanism, activation parameters.

Introduction

Platinum complexes are biologically important because of their anticancer activities. In particular, the interaction of DNA with Pt^{II} complexes has been extensively studied¹. Substitution reactions on square planar platinum(II) complexes have attracted continued attention because of their intrinsic chemical^{2,3} and biomedical applications^{4,5}. Specifically *cis*-platin⁶, [*cis*-dichlorodiamineplatinum(II)], and its structural analogues⁷ have been used in cancer chemotherapy. At present it is believed that DNA is the main target of these drugs in tumor cells⁸. Binding to proteins and peptides also occurs as has been shown by many investigators^{9,10}. It is widely recognized that the two nonleaving spectator *cis*-nitrogen ligands are still attached to platinum when the drugs reaches their target in cellular DNA¹¹. When a chloro drug is administered, the chloride ions are displaced by a hydrolytic process and the hydrolytic product undergoes favorable and active nucleophilic substitution by the DNA base sites¹². But the major drawback of these chloro derivatives of (*N,N*)-chelated platinum(II) complexes has been their nephrotoxicity⁷. So the search for other drugs continues; the

aqua variety, however, has been found to be superior¹³ to others. Apart from this, certain proteolytic enzymes require metal ions for activity and metal complexes hold great promise as cleaving reagents¹⁴. Some *N,N* bound platinum(II) complexes bind to the side chain of methionine, histidine, arginine, and cysteine residue of certain proteins and result in selective hydrolytic cleavage of adjacent amide bond¹⁵. In view of greater affinity of platinum for nitrogen and sulfur-containing ligands, it is of interest to investigate their reaction with amino acids and peptides. It is believed that the platinum(II) complexes derived their antitumor activity from their interactions with some enzymes connected with cell division¹⁶. Kinetic and mechanistic descriptions of the reactions between *cis*-(*N,N*)-chelated diaquaplatinum(II) ions with proteins and their amino acid fragments are now a subject of interest¹⁷. In order to examine the reactivity of aqua amine complexes of platinum(II) towards substituted nucleic acid and substituted amino acids, this paper deals with the interaction of 2-thiouracil with *cis*-diaqua(ethylenediamine) platinum(II) perchlorate in an aqueous medium. In this

Fig. 1. A typical plot of $\ln(A_{\infty} - A_t)$ versus time : $[\text{Complex 1}] = 1.85 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{2-thiouracil}] = 3.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\Delta = X - Y$, indicates the difference in absorbances between two steps in different time interval, $\text{pH} = 4.0$, $\text{Temp.} = 30 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

connection, some of my lab mate have already studied the kinetics of aqua ligand substitution of *cis*- $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ by different bioactive ligands such as cysteine, methionine, adenosine, thiourea¹⁸ etc. In the present paper we describe the kinetics of aqua ligand substitution of $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ by 2-thiouracil under different experimental conditions.

Results and discussion

The pK_1 and pK_2 values^{19,20} of 2-thiouracil are 9.78, 12.7 respectively at 25 °C. Thus at pH 4.0, the ligand exists mainly in neutral form.

On the other hand the acid dissociation equilibrium of the complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{2+}$ are

At pH 4.0 the complex mainly exists in the diaqua form and it is evident that the reaction is mainly due to the interaction between the diaqua form of the complex and neutral form of the ligand.

The plots of $\ln(A_{\infty} - A_t)$, where A_t and A_{∞} are absorbances at time t and after the completion of the reaction, against time were found to be non linear, being curved at

the initial stage and subsequently of constant slope (Fig. 1).

The method of Weyh and Hamm²¹ was adopted to calculate rate constants for two consecutive steps. From the linear second portion k_2 values were obtained. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values were obtained from the plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus t . A typical plot is shown in Fig. 2. Rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs are reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Fig. 2. A typical plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus time (min) : $[\text{Complex 1}] = 1.85 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{2-thiouracil}] = 3.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.0$, $\text{temp.} = 30 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The rate constant for such a process can be evaluated by assuming the Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Representation of reaction scheme.

where A is complex (1), B is as intermediate with 2-thiouracil and C is the final product complex [Pt(en)(2-thiouracil)]⁺.

Calculation of k_1 for $A \rightarrow B$ step :

The rate constant $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ for the $A \rightarrow B$ step can be evaluated by the method of Weyh and Hamm using the usual consecutive rate law :

$$(A_\infty - A_t) - a_2 \exp(-k_2 t) = a_1 \exp(-k_{1(\text{obs})} t) \quad (3)$$

where a_1 and a_2 are constants dependent upon the rate constants and extinction coefficient.

Values of $[(A_\infty - A_t) - a_2 \exp(-k_2 t)]$ were obtained from X-Y at different times (Fig. 1).

Then,

$$\ln \Delta = \text{constant} - k_{1(\text{obs})} t \quad (4)$$

The value of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ was derived from the slope of a plot of $\ln \Delta$ versus t (where t is small) (Fig. 2). A similar procedure was applied for each 2-thiouracil concentration in the 1.85×10^{-3} to 5.55×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ range, at constant [(1)] (1.85×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) and pH = 4.0, $\mu = 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ and at different temperatures namely 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C. The $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values are collected in Table 1.

The rate increases with increase in [2-thiouracil] before reaching a limiting value (Fig. 3), which is probably due to the completion of the outer-sphere association complex formation. At this stage the interchange of the ligands

Table 1. $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s⁻¹) values for different thiouracil concentrations at different temperatures

[Complex 1] = 1.85×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, pH = 4.0, ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄

10^3 [Thiouracil] (mol dm ⁻³)	Temp. (°C)			
	30	35	40	45
1.85	2.36	3.44	4.56	5.01
2.77	3.02	4.36	5.48.	6.30
3.7	3.62	4.99	6.25	6.99
5.55	4.35	5.55	7.14	7.81

from the outer-sphere to the inner-sphere occurs, i.e. 2-thiouracil attacks the Pt^{II} of the complex (1) to give the intermediate complex.

From the experimental findings the following scheme can be proposed;

where L-LH is the neutral form of 2-thiouracil

Scheme 2. Formation of substituted complex.

Based on Scheme 2 a rate expression can be derived for the $A \rightarrow B$ step;

$$d[B]/dt = k_1 K_E [B] [2\text{-thiouracil}] / (1 + K_E [2\text{-thiouracil}]) \quad (8)$$

$$d[B]/dt = k_{1(\text{obs})} [B]_T$$

where T stands for total concentration of Pt^{II}. Thus it can be written,

$$k_{1(\text{obs})} = k_1 K_E [2\text{-thiouracil}] / (1 + K_E [2\text{-thiouracil}]) \quad (9)$$

The equation can be written as

$$1/k_{1(\text{obs})} = 1/k_1 + 1/k_1 K_E [2\text{-thiouracil}] \quad (10)$$

A plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ versus $1/[2\text{-thiouracil}]$ should therefore be linear with an intercept of $1/k_1$ and slope $1/k_1 K_E$. This was found to be so at all temperatures studied (Fig. 4).

The k_1 and K_E values obtained from the intercept and slope to intercept ratios are given in Table 2.

Calculation of k_2 for the step $B \rightarrow C$:

The $B \rightarrow C$ step is intramolecular ring closure and is independent of ligand concentration. At a particular tem-

Fig. 3. Plot of $k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) versus [2-thiouracil] (mol dm^{-3}) at different temperatures : A = 30, B = 35, C = 40 and D = 45 °C.

Fig. 4. Plot of $1/k_{1(\text{obs})}$ (s^{-1}) versus $1/[2\text{-thiouracil}]$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) at different temperatures : A = 30, B = 35, C = 40 and D = 45 °C.

Table 2. k_1 and K_E values for the substitution reaction at different temperatures

[Complex 1] = $1.85 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 4.0, ionic strength = $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaClO}_4$

Temp. (°C)	$10^3 k_1$ (s^{-1})	K_E ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)
30	7.56	244.46
35	8.36	383.33
40	10.0	454.55
45	11.0	457.56

perature the slope of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ versus time plots at different 2-thiouracil concentrations were found to be constant in the region where the plots are linear (Fig. 1). For

different temperatures the k_2 values were obtained directly from the limiting slopes and are collected in Table 3 and the average $10^5 \times k_2$ values were 3.53, 4.39, 5.07 and 6.09 s^{-1} at 30, 35, 40 and 45 °C respectively.

Table 3. $10^5 k_2$ (s^{-1}) values for different 2-thiouracil concentrations at different temperatures

[Complex 1] = $1.85 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, pH = 4.0, ionic strength = $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaClO}_4$

10^3 [2-Thiouracil] (mol dm^{-3})	Temp. (°C)			
	30	35	40	45
1.85	3.55	4.36	5.05	6.02
2.77	3.47	4.38	5.09	6.06
3.70	3.57	4.39	5.10	6.12
5.55	3.53	4.41	5.02	6.15

Effects of pH on the reaction rate :

The reaction was studied at five different pH values. At a fixed $1.85 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ [Complex 1], $3.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ [2-thiouracil] and $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ NaClO}_4$ ionic strength, the $10^3 k_{1(\text{obs})}$ values were 2.8, 3.2, 3.4, 3.64, and 3.87 and $10^5 k_2$ values were 2.25, 3.02, 3.57, 5.3 and 8.84 at pH 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5 and 5.0 respectively at 30 °C. The change in rate may be explained based on two acid dissociation equilibria of the ligand and the complex. Firstly, within our studied pH range the ligand, 2-thiouracil remains unchanged so the effects of pH on rate are therefore due to the change in reactive forms of the reacting complex.

Fig. 5. Eyring plot for k_1 .

Fig. 6. Eyring plot for k_2 .

Effects of temperature on the reaction rate :

Four different temperatures were chosen for study and the results are listed in Tables 2 and 3. The activation parameters for the steps $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow C$ were evaluated from the linear Eyring plots (Figs. 5 and 6) and the results are compared with analogous systems in Table 4.

Mechanism and conclusion :

The starting complex does not react well with azide, cytidine or with thymidine, but easily reacts with sulphur-containing molecules such as cysteine, thiosemicarbazide, methionine *etc.* So we may say that the sulphur atom of the ligand is involved in bonding with Pt^{II} due to the soft nature of both the atoms. Our results indicate that the first step, i.e. the attack by the incoming ligand (2-thiouracil) proceeds by an associative interchange (I_a) mechanism. This proposition is supported by the following observations. First, with an increase in ligand concentration, saturation in the rate is observed. This indicates that an outer-sphere association complex is formed. Second, the low enthalpy of activation and large negative value of entropy of activation strongly suggest that the ligand participates in the transition state.

As the result of Job's method of continuous variation indicate 1 : 1 molar ratio and the IR spectrum of the solid product suggests that 2-thiouracil behave, as a bidentate

Table 4. Activation parameters for substitution of [Complex 1] by various ligands in aqueous medium, pH = 4.0

Ligand	ΔH_1^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_1^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH_2^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_2^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	Ref.
L-Asparagine	43.59 ± 0.9	-116.98 ± 2.9	33.78 ± 0.51	-221.43 ± 1.5	22
DL-Methionine	15.6 ± 0.9	-230 ± 3	19.5 ± 1.20	-226 ± 4.0	22
DL-Penicillamine	46.5 ± 5.0	-143 ± 15	44.3 ± 1.3	-189 ± 4.2	22
2-Thiouracil	18.3 ± 1.8	-225 ± 6	25.9 ± 1.4	-148 ± 4.5	This work

ligand. This is consistent with the soft nature of both sulphur and platinum(II). Finally ESI-mass spectra provide a qualitative picture of the composition i.e. the ligational sites are the sulfur and nitrogen ends of 2-thiouracil. The affinity of nitrogen atom of the 2-thiouracil provides the driving force for the ring formation. Thus 2-thiouracil behaves as a chelating ligand within the experimental pH range^{32,33}.

The activation parameters ($\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 18.3 \pm 1.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^\ddagger = -225 \pm 6 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) for the first step and the second step ($\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 25.9 \pm 1.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_2^\ddagger = -148 \pm 4.5 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) suggest an associative mode of activation for the substitution process. In the first step a rapid equilibrium is established, giving an outer-sphere complex between complex 1 and 2-thiouracil. The second step is the intra-molecular ring closure which is independent on the incoming ligand concentration. Hence, the rate constant (k_2) for this step was independent of ligand concentration.

It was also found that after completion of the reaction, the pH decreases and conductance of the resulting solution was increased, which might be due to loss of one proton in the first step, consequently ring closure occurs through nitrogen atom.

Based on the experimental results described above, we propose the reaction mechanism shown in Scheme 3.

Experimental

Materials :

The complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (Complex 1) was prepared according to the literature²³; characterized spectroscopically²⁴ ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 256 \text{ nm}$) and by elemental analysis (Found : C, 7.30; H, 2.48; N, 8.60. Calcd. for $\text{C}_2\text{H}_8\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{Pt}$: C, 7.36; H, 2.45; N, 8.59%). Complex 1 and the ligand were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio in a reaction vessel and heated at 60 °C for 72 h, then transferred in a glass beaker and slowly evaporated at room temperature and finally in a desiccators. This product was used for IR and ESI-MS spectroscopic analysis. The pH of the solution was so maintained (pH = 4.0) that >90% of the perchlorate salt was obtained as diaqua species. The reaction product of 2-thiouracil ($3.7 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and complex 1 ($1.85 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were prepared by mixing the reactants in different ratios namely 1 : 5, 1 : 10, 1 : 20, and 1 : 30 and equilibrating the mixture at $30 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 48 h. The absorption spectra of these mixtures (Fig. 7) all exhibited the same λ_{max} with nearly identical intensities.

Scheme 3. Proposed probable mechanism for the interaction of 2-thiouracil with complex 1.

Fig. 7. Spectra of the starting [Complex 1] (1), and the 2-thiouracil substituted complex (2) : [Complex 1] = 1.85×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [2-thiouracil] = 3.7×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, pH = 4.0, cell used = 1 cm quartz.

Product analysis :

The composition of the product was determined by Job's method of continuous variation, which indicated a 1 : 1 metal ligand ratio (Fig. 8).

Complex 1 and 2-thiouracil were mixed in 1 : 1 molar ratio at pH 4.0 and a yellowish product was obtained. The IR spectra of the yellowish product in the KBr disc show strong bands at 3458 and 526 cm⁻¹. The presence of a strong -OH stretching band at 3458 cm⁻¹ indicates that product contained free -OH group. The absence of

weak absorption of the -SH group at 2466 cm⁻¹, present in free 2-thiouracil, indicate formation of the Pt-S bond in the product complex²⁵. The band at 526 cm⁻¹ is also assigned to $\nu(\text{Pt-N})$ bond formation²⁶. The spectrum suggests that the final product is an S, N coordinated chelate and the 2-thiouracil behave as a bidentate ligand in the experimental pH.

The aqueous solution of *cis*-[Pt(en)(OH₂)₂]²⁺ and 2-thiouracil were mixed in a 1 : 1 molar ratio and the mixture was thermostated at 60 °C for 48 h and used for

Fig. 8. Job's plot for the reaction between complex 1 and 2-thiouracil at pH = 4.0 and ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄.

Fig. 9. ESI-mass spectra of the product.

ESI-MS measurement. The ESI mass spectra of the resulting solution are shown in Fig. 9.

It is clear from this spectrum that the ion at $m/z \sim 382$ has become the molecular ion species in the solution mixture and this is attributed to $[2\text{-thiouracil anion} + \text{Pt}^{\text{II}} + \text{en}]^+$.

The precursor ion is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Plausible structure of the molecular ion peak from the ESI-mass spectra.

Measurements :

All the spectral scanning and kinetic measurements were done in a Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV-2450 PC), attached to a thermoelectric cell temperature controller (model TCC-240A with an accuracy of ± 0.1 °C). IR spectra (KBr disc, $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were measured in Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 Infrared spectrophotometer. ESI-mass spectra recorded using a micromass Q-Tof microTM mass spectrometer in positive ion mode.

The pHs of the solutions were adjusted with $\text{HClO}_4/\text{NaOH}$ and measured with a Sartorius pH meter (model PB11) with an accuracy of ± 0.01 . Milli Q water was used to prepare all the solutions. All other chemicals used were of AR grade. The reactions were carried out at constant ionic strength ($0.1\text{ mol dm}^{-3}\text{ NaClO}_4$).

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